

2,4-Distyryl-7,8-benzoquinoline (II)

2,4-Dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline (15.1 g) and freshly distilled benzaldehyde (36 g) were refluxed for 32 hr in presence of acetic anhydride. The excess of benzaldehyde was removed by steam distillation. The liquid was poured in 100 ml of 20% NaOH solution. Yellow mass separated. Recrystallised from a mixture of benzene and ether petrol (60°–80°). Yellow crystals (19 g), m.p. 180°–81°. It gives bluish fluorescence with benzene, acetone, ethanol and ether. (Found: C, 90.1; H, 6.0. $C_{29}H_{21}N$ requires C, 9.08; H, 5.48%), ν_{max} 1600 and 1577 (–CH = CH–) 733 (four adjacent H), 850 (two adjacent H), 8,80–894 cm^{-1} (one isolated H).

2,4-Di-(3'-nitro)styryl-7,8-benzoquinoline (III)

A mixture of 2,4-dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline (20.7 g), *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (30.2 g) and acetic anhydride (10 ml) was heated at 160° for 4 hr. The mixture was poured in 200 ml of 20% NaOH solution. The yellow mass separated. Recrystallised from xylene. Yellow crystals m.p. 281°–82°. It was insoluble in benzene, chloroform and ethanol. (Found: C, 73.4; H, 4.2. $C_{29}H_{19}N_3O_4$ requires C, 73.5; H, 4.1%), ν_{max} 1600 and 1576 (–CH = CH–), 724 (four adjacent H), 820 (three adjacent H), 870 (one isolated H), 1516 and 1341 cm^{-1} (–NO₂).

7,8-Benzoquinoline-2,4-dicarboxylic acid (IV)

This was prepared following the procedure of Singh and Lal³. Recrystallised from a mixture of ethanol and ether petrol (60°–80°). Yellow crystals, m.p. 262°–63° (decomp.). It is insoluble in ether, benzene, acetone but soluble in alcohol. (Found: C, 67.6; H, 3.0. $C_{15}H_9NO_4$ requires C, 67.4; H, 3.3%), ν_{max} 1685 (C = O), 3000 (OH, hydrogen bonded), 740 (four adjacent H), 830 (two adjacent H) and 880 cm^{-1} (one isolated H).

7,8-Benzoquinoline (V)

A mixture of 2,4-dicarboxyl-7,8-benzoquinoline (0.4 g) and sodalime (0.5 g) was heated strongly. A few drops of yellow liquid deposited which solidified as yellowish brown crystals, m.p. 51°–52°, picrate m.p. 190°–91°. (Found: C, 87.5; H, 5.0. $C_{13}H_9N$ requires C, 87.1; H, 5.02%).

Oxidation of 2,4-dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline with SeO₂

2,4-Dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline (I, 1.2 g) and SeO₂ (2 g) were refluxed for 16 hr in ethanol (20 ml). The solution was evaporated to dryness and residue was taken up in acetone. 30% H₂O₂ (5 ml) was added and mixture refluxed for 1 hr. Acetone was removed and solid residue was extracted with ethanol and solution was concentrated. Yellow crystals were obtained. Recrystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 260°–61° with blackening at 258°. (Found: C, 66.9; H, 3.5. $C_{15}H_9NO_4$ requires C, 67.4; H, 3.3%), ν_{max} 1685 (C = O), 3000 (broad, H bonding), 740 (four adjacent H), 830 (two adjacent H), 880 (one isolated H).

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A New Method Depending on the Use of the Rotating Pt-Electrode at Zero applied e.m.f. for Micro-determination of Nitrite

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CHOW and Robinson¹ determined nitrite polarographically in presence of MoO₄²⁻ as catalyst. Several oxidants were previously described for the determination of nitrite depending upon its oxidation to nitrate²⁻⁷. Recently, Issa *et al.*⁸ determined nitrite by back titration with KMnO₄ in fluoride medium and the lower limit of nitrite determined was 0.093 mg.

In the present investigation, we describe a new method for microdetermination of nitrite. It depends upon amperometric titration with potassium permanganate in acid medium containing fluoride ions using the rotating Pt-electrode vs S.O.E. as reference at zero applied e.m.f. The factors affecting the success of the method are studied.

Experimental

Reagents

Preparation of solutions: Potassium permanganate solutions were prepared by a method similar to that of Stamm⁹ and standardized with sodium oxalate¹⁰ (normality of permanganate solutions used is based on valency change of Mn⁺⁷ to Mn⁺³). Sodium nitrite solutions were prepared by dissolving the A.R. product in double distilled water and standardized according to recommended procedure⁴. Solutions of permanganate and nitrite of required concentrations were obtained by appropriate dilution. Other solutions including 2% sodium fluoride, 1N sulfuric acid and 0.5N copper sulfate were prepared from the A.R. chemicals.

Titration procedure

The amperometric titration assembly used consisted of a beaker, rotating Pt-electrode, agar bridge, saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.) and microburette. The attainment of a steady diffusion current was maintained by rotating the Pt-electrode at a constant speed of 600 r.p.m. The nitrite solution was mixed with the appropriate amount of sulfuric acid and/or with sulfuric acid, sodium fluoride and copper sulfate,

completed to a known volume (usually 10 ml) with double distilled water and titrated with permanganate. The diffusion current corrected for dilution was calculated for dilution and plotted against the volume of permanganate. The dilution correction is made by multiplying the current measured by a factor of $V + v/v$ where V is the original volume and v is the volume of titrant added.

Results and Discussions

Effect of acidity: Table 1 shows the effect of acidity on the accuracy of the end point. Good results corresponding to oxidation of nitrite to nitrate are obtained at acidities ranging from 0.05 to 0.25N H₂SO₄. At higher acid concentrations, earlier end points are obtained as a result of partial reduction of permanganate to bivalent manganese and the probable escape of nitrous acid at higher acidities. The titration curves are nearly reversed L-shaped.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF ACIDITY

Titration of 3 ml 0.081N NaNO₂ with 0.074N KMnO₄ in presence of 5 ml 2% NaF and 1 ml 0.5N CuSO₄ at different acidities. (Total volume 10 ml.)

Acidity N H ₂ SO ₄	Vol. of KMnO ₄ consumed (ml)	Theoretical end point (ml)	Error (%, ±)
0.05	3.27	3.28	0.30
0.15	3.26	3.28	0.60
0.20	3.27	3.28	0.30
0.25	3.25	3.28	0.91
0.30	3.15	3.28	3.96

Effect of CuSO₄ concentration: The results recorded in Table 2, show that the presence of CuSO₄ has not much influence on the accuracy of the results. However, the important role played by Cu²⁺ is mainly restricted to improve the detection of the end point.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF CuSO₄ CONCENTRATION

Titration of 3 ml 0.081N KMnO₄ with 0.074N KMnO₄ in presence of 0.2N H₂SO₄ and 5 ml 2% NaF. (Total volume 10 ml.)

Vol. of 0.5N CuSO ₄ (ml)	Vol. of KMnO ₄ consumed (ml)	Theoretical end point (ml)	Error (%, ±)
—	3.30	3.28	0.60
0.5	3.29	3.28	0.30
1	3.27	3.28	0.30
4	3.27	3.28	0.30
6	3.26	3.28	0.60

Effect of NaF concentration: Good end points are obtained when the sodium fluoride concentration varies from 0.8–1.5% (Table 3).

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF NaF CONCENTRATION

Titration of 3 ml 0.081N NaNO₂ with 0.074N KMnO₄ in presence of 0.2 N H₂SO₄ and 1 ml 0.5 N CuSO₄. (Total volume ~ 10 ml.)

Vol. of 2% NaF (ml)	Vol. of KMnO ₄ consumed (ml)	Theoretical end point (ml)	Error (%, ±)
3	2.95	3.28	10.00
4	3.26	3.28	0.60
6	3.28	3.28	Nil

Effect of Sodium Nitrite concentration: Table 4 shows that amounts of sodium nitrite ranging from 6.9 μg to 13.97 mg can be determined accurately by amperometric titration with KMnO₄ in presence of 0.02N H₂SO₄, 0.05N CuSO₄ and 1% NaF.

Nitrite can be oxidized to nitrate quantitatively with permanganate in fluoride medium⁸ according to the following equation:

TABLE 4—DETERMINATION OF DIFFERENT AMOUNTS OF NITRITE

Titration of different concentrations of nitrite with KMnO₄ in presence of 0.2N H₂SO₄, 0.05N CuSO₄ and 1% NaF

Vol & Normality of NaNO ₂		Amounts of NaNO ₂ (mg)	Vol. & Normality of KMnO ₄		Theoretical end point (ml)	Error (%±)	Total volume (ml)
(ml)	(N)		(ml)	(N)			
0.5	4.01 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.0069	0.543	3.7 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.547	0.73	10
1	4.01 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.0138	1.093	3.7 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.095	0.10	10
3	4.01 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.0414	3.27	3.7 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.284	0.43	10
0.5	4.01 × 10 ⁻³	0.069	0.55	3.7 × 10 ⁻³	0.547	0.54	10
3	4.01 × 10 ⁻³	0.414	3.28	3.7 × 10 ⁻³	3.284	0.12	10
0.2	0.081	0.56	0.22	0.074	0.219	0.45	10
0.5	0.081	1.39	0.55	0.074	0.547	0.54	10
5	0.081	13.97	5.43	0.074	5.47	0.73	20

The amperometric method exhibits many advantages than the other titrimetric methods. Since permanganate is reduced at almost zero applied e.m.f., deaeration of the solution containing the reducible material is not necessary. Furthermore the amperometric method is more rapid and simple, where the equivalent point can be determined from few readings before and after the end point. Therefore, the amperometric method can be considered as a good analytical tool for determining amounts of sodium nitrite as low as 6.9 μg , whereas the lower amount determined by the potentiometric method was 0.093 mg⁸.

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Synthesis of I-5, II-5, I-7, II-7-Tetramethoxy [I-8, II-8] Biflavone

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ONE of the common methods employed for the synthesis of various naturally occurring biflavonoids^{1,2} is simple or crossed Ullmann reaction²⁻⁶. Generally the dimers are obtained in low yields.

I-5, II-5, I-7, II-7-Tetramethoxy [I-8, II-8] biflavone has now been synthesised from the corresponding biphenyl derivatives. The mono iodination of xanthoxylin gave 2-hydroxy-3-iodo-4,6-dimethoxyacetophenone⁷ (I). This underwent reaction with copper bronze at 280° to give 2,2'-dihydroxy-4,4', 6,6'-tetramethoxy-3,3'-diacetyl biphenyl (IIa) (ν_{max} 1630 cm^{-1}). The compound (IIa) on benzylation gave 2,2'-dibenzoyloxy-4,4', 6,6'-tetramethoxy-3,3'-diacetyl biphenyl (IIb) (ν_{max} 1690 cm^{-1}), which underwent rearrangement when heated with acetone and potassium carbonate to give 4,4', 6,6'-tetramethoxy-2,2'-dihydroxy-3,3'-di(ω -benzoyl acetyl) biphenyl (IIc) (ν_{max} 1630 and 1690 cm^{-1}). On acid cyclisation this gave an almost quantitative yield of the biflavone (III) (ν_{max} 1645 cm^{-1}). In the mass spectrum of (III) the molecular ion appeared at m/e 562 and the general

fragmentation pattern was typical of a C-C linked biflavone⁸

- (a) R = CH₃; R₁ = H; R₂ = OCH₃
 (b) R = CH₃; R₁ = COC₆H₅; R₂ = OCH₃
 (c) R = CH₂COC₆H₅; R₁ = COC₆H₅; R₂ = OCH₃

Experimental

(a) 2,2'-Dihydroxy-4,4', 6,6'-tetramethoxy-3,3'-diacetyl biphenyl

A mixture of 2-hydroxy-3-iodo-4,6-dimethoxyacetophenone (5 g), copper bronze (15 g) and dimethyl formamide (100 ml) was refluxed in a metal bath for 4 hr, filtered hot and washed with 15 ml of solvent. Water (200 ml) was added to the combined filtrate and washings and left overnight. The precipitate was filtered and recrystallised from dimethylformamide-water as colourless needles, m.p. 185°-186° (found: C, 61.3; H, 5.56; Mol. wt. (Rast method), 372; C₂₀H₂₂O₈ requires C, 61.53; H, 5.64%; mol. wt., 390).

(b) 4,4', 6,6'-Tetramethoxy-2,2'-dibenzoyloxy-3,3'-diacetyl biphenyl

A mixture of 4,4', 6,6'-tetramethoxy-2,2'-dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetyl biphenyl (11.8 g), benzoyl chloride (8.4 g) and pyridine (30 ml) was heated on steam bath for 15 min, poured into water and stirred with dil. HCl and then with dilute alcohol. After it had solidified the product was washed with dilute alcohol, dried at room temperature and crystallised from alcohol-water as colourless plates, m.p. 78°-79° (found: C, 67.65; H, 5.1; C₃₁H₃₀O₁₀ requires C, 68.23; H, 5.02%).